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Story

I'm going to start from the most innocuous axiom anyone can possibly start from. The idea that there is a story. In my head right now, there's a story. In your life, there's a narrative, there's always some story. Undeniable, to the point where it's kind of a non-axiom.

Now, I have to explain where this story comes from, and one natural approach is to say it's a story of storytellers who tell the story. That closes a loop, it's a self-referential loop, but it explains everything I need right away. This approach is called idealism. Notice one thing quickly, this statement that we have a story of storytellers who tell the story, is an idealist reading of the anthropic principle. So, in idealism the anthropic principle reduces trivially to idealism itself.

And if you're wondering why can't we close the loop with singular storyteller? I want you to hold that thought we're going to come back to it later in the talk.

The problem with this approach is that it is only not absurd if you can explain why many storytellers tell the same exact story. You can think of this as an absurdity gate. Apparently this was not a very easy gate to get past, and it was much easier to just backtrack and take an entirely opposite approach.

And that opposite approach is called materialism, where you say that the story is driven by objective reality that sits outside of the storytellers, and you don't call them storytellers anymore, you call them observers. Remember, idealism was idealism because we did not appeal to an external objective reality. Now that we've appealed to an external objective reality, it's called materialism.

And this materialist approach has its own version of the absurdity gate we encountered on the idealism branch. In materialism, the gate says that materialism is not absurd only if objective reality is oblivious to the observers and not contrived to accommodate their existence. I want to stress that this is not a new gate, it's the flipside of the gate on the idealism branch. The identity between the two gates forces the strong language used for the gate on the right. This strong language prohibits us from trying to split the baby and have it both ways.

To see this, think of the absurdity gates as an absurdity complementarity principle, meaning the moment you start relaxing this requirement that objective reality is oblivious to the observers and not contrived to accommodate their existence, you are essentially saying that the storytellers/observers are telling at least part of the story and you immediately trigger the absurdity of not having an explanation for why many storytellers are telling the same exact story.

I want to point out quickly here that this absurdity complementarity principle is not purely theoretical. There is a real life example of a physicist who tried to split the baby. Remember, instead of a story of storytellers who tell the story, you actually have a physicist who proposed a story of participatory observers. Participatory observers sits right in between storytellers and observers. And that physicist is of course John Wheeler. And out of all physicists, John Wheeler was likely the one most tormented by a lack of an answer to this question of why we have shared reality. What I'm saying is that that is not a coincidence. It's this absurdity complementarity principle in action.

As you're no doubt starting to see here, there's a symmetry developing between the two approaches. Each has its own main problem and a secondary problem. The main problems are shown here in the blue textboxes and I will show the secondary problems in purple textboxes. The secondary problem on the materialism side is explaining the illusion of free will, which we're all familiar with.

The corresponding secondary problem on the left side, on the idealism side, is what I call **Authorial Disavowal**, meaning the illusion of passive observation. This is when you author something and then immediately proceed to delete any evidence or record of its authorship. The best way to appreciate our capacity for authorial disavowal is to think about dreams. We author our own dreams yet we believe they are happening to us. And the best way to understand authorial disavowal is to appreciate that the loop of story of storytellers who tell the story doesn't quite close if the storytellers don't disavow their authorship.

Pause for a moment to think about the capacity for self deception required for dreams to work the way they do. For you to be able to both secretly author your dream and believe that it's happening To you. Is it really that much of a leap at that point to claim that waking reality is a group exercise in self deception? What if dreams are periodic solo practice sessions in self deception required to sustain the high-level ensemble performance of waking reality? Finally, if proper closure of self reference loops truly does require authorial disavowal as I claim it does then why haven't we encountered this in explorations of self-reference.

Gödel sentence:

“This sentence is not provable in this formal system.”

Many have used Gödel’s incompleteness theorem to argue for a mind-independent “objective” truth/reality

In making these arguments, one easily achieves the goal of authorial disavowal because there is no authorship to begin with in a mind-independent objective reality

Well, what if we have encountered it without recognizing it. What if Godel sentences are the quintessential example of authorial disavowal. “This sentence is not provable in this formal system.”

If you just replace provable by authored, it’s a perfect match.

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Now if it’s true that Gödel’s sentences are the quintessential example of authorial disavowal, and if as I claim, authorial disavowal is the method by which one deceives one’s self into believing in objective reality (thereby closing the loop), then I am essentially saying that something like Gödel’s incompleteness theorem is the method by which we deceive ourselves into believing in objective reality.

And as it turns out, many have indeed appealed to Gödel’s incompleteness theorem to argue for a mind-independent “objective” reality

As I mentioned earlier, the absurdity gate triggered very early on, on the left branch and caused us to backtrack and take the right branch, which is materialism. And we actually did really well on this materialist branch for a very long time. Until in the 1970s, when we discovered that the values a very large number of parameters in our best model of physics called the standard model are contrived to ensure the existence of the physicists authoring it. And at that point, whether we know it or not, the absurdity gate, as expressed on the right, triggered and ejected us over to the left branch. So my viewpoint is that we were ejected from materialist physics to idealist physics all the way back in the 1970s and we just didn't know it. And we continue not to know it. This ejection is evidenced by the complete lack of major advances in theoretical physics since the 1970's.

I want to clarify that I'm making a very strange claim about our trajectory in this decision tree. I claim we've been setup, we've been manipulated. With the spectacular capacity for self deception described earlier as the background, I want to turn now to the question posed at the beginning of this talk: why can't we close the loop with a singular storyteller. Let's deal with this question now.

The plurality of storytellers does seem peculiar. To make it less peculiar we have to find some reason or purpose for it. What purpose does plural storytellers serve here... well we wouldn't have the absurdity gate if we didn't have the plurality of storytellers to begin with. And we wouldn't have been redirected into materialism had it not been for that absurdity gate. And who benefits from our redirection towards materialism? Can anyone guess? It's our old friend Authorial Disavowal. There is no authorship to be disavowed on the materialist branch. So, to the extent that authorial disavowal is needed to close the loop, plural storytellers are needed. In this way one can come to understand both the plurality of storytellers and possibly even why they tell the same story.

I'm showing here the URL for a preprint that gives an answer to this question of why many storytellers tell the same story. At the time I discovered this answer, I had not yet discovered authorial disavowal so it currently does not appeal to authorial disavowal. Originally, my plan was to spend the rest of this talk going over this answer, but what happened was that - having gained entry into this landscape of idealism- I couldn't resist starting my exploration. Remember this is completely fertile ground, because everyone else is on the right side of this decision tree in materialism world—so the first ten minutes of exploration were action-packed. I'd like to, instead, spend the rest of this talk sharing what I found.

I'm actually going to proceed down this path in a way that salvages our efforts on the right. What I mean by that is as follows. I am going to take idealism as the truth, because that's what going down the left branch means. But from this viewpoint of idealism, I'm going to model the experience of a materialist physicist, meaning a physicist who stubbornly refuses to accept what I believe to be the truth, which is idealism. Now, keep in mind that even though I claim that we were ejected from materialism onto idealism back in the 1970s, most physicists today do not believe this and materialism continues today to be the predominant view in physics. So to the extent that my modeling of a materialist physicist's experience from the point of view of idealism ends up matching what current physics is experiencing today, that would be a very strong sign that idealism is the correct branch.

One last thing before I get started: I'd like to set expectations. I am modeling the experience of a materialist physicist sitting all the way on the top right, very deep up in the materialist branch of the decision tree of science and philosophy from all the way down here at the very start of the idealist branch of that decision tree. We're talking about maybe a billion physicist year gap between these two points. I am therefore not at all expecting that my model will predict word for word exactly and with accurate equations what the materialist physicist's experience is today. I am expecting the model to rhyme at best.

Seated so far down the materialist branch of the decision tree, this physicist no doubt believes he is close to the answer even though he has now been close to the answer for over a hundred years already. If my model anticipates anything specific it would be this physicist's retort that rhymes are for poets. And that's fine by me. At 100 years old, the problem of understanding quantum mechanics has now graduated to a species level problem. It is not for this physicist or that physicist to solve anymore. It's now time for us lift the gates. For the poets, the artists, the mathematicians, and the philosophers to step in.

The first step is to note that story of storytellers who tell the story is a grand self-referential loop. And it's also important to note that the materialist physicist will be blind to this self-referential loop because they won't say story of storytellers who tell the story, they will simply say story of observers, thereby breaking the loop and being unable to see it or acknowledge that it's there.

Picture boundary hack

I want to start with a visual of this grand self referential loop. I spent an hour or two (yes, I lied about the 10 minutes part) trying to convince gpt to give me a drawing of a physicist zooming in on himself and didn't get anywhere. Eventually I settled for the hack of drawing the physicist zooming in on a picture of himself rather than his actual self. I call this the picture boundary hack. This hack immediately produces a Droste effect of course because it's a picture inside itself. Original Droste is shown on the right. In all these Droste effect pictures you have a larger outer image that's understood in 3D, meaning in the larger outer background you understand that there is a 3D woman holding a box with what's understood as a bordered 2D picture. The larger outer background is understood as representing objective reality with the smaller bordered picture representing art or subjective reality.

Rhyme 1: Representation of objective reality restricted to the large world in both Droste and QM.

Immediately we have a rhyme with quantum mechanics. This breakdown of Droste reminds me of the scene from National Geographic's anthology series, GENIUS where Einstein is almost hit by a car that he didn't see coming and quips to Neils bhor that he was almost run over by a car that didn't exist. In Quantum mechanics, just as in Droste pictures, the materialist's representation of objective reality is restricted to the larger macroscopic background. This is our first rhyme.

1956: Escher tries to remove border

Now soon after settling for the bordered picture hack, I found out that I was in good company earlier when I tried (and failed) to avoid it. Escher himself tried avoiding it in his famous Print Gallery shown here on the right but only half succeeded. You can see the drawing is unfinished in the center where Escher just left his signature instead.

Rhyme 2: Border turns out to not be fundamental to Droste and undefinable in QM (Copenhagen famously refuses to say where the boundary is drawn between classical and quantum mechanics).

1956: Escher tries to remove border

2003: Mathematicians finish the job

Close to half a century later in 2003 mathematicians finish the job. Here, we have two new rhymes. First, we have the fact that the border turns out to not be fundamental to Droste and undefinable in QM (Copenhagen famously refuses to say where the boundary is drawn between classical and quantum mechanics).

Solution to problem of removing border from Droste leads to:

Bart de Smit: "A continuous interpolation between the straight world and the curved world"

Rhyme 3: Border in both Droste and QM is at the interface between linear and nonlinear.

This rhymes with QM in the sense that a linear equation (Schrodinger) is used for quantum, but collapses when transitioning to classical.

1956: Escher tries to remove border

2003: Mathematicians finish the job

Furthermore, as you can see from Print Gallery, removal of the border requires a transition from straight to curved lines. In the words of the mathematician who solved the problem of removing the border, the solution leads to:

"A continuous interpolation between the straight world and the curved world"

This rhymes with QM in the sense that a linear equation-schrodinger's equation-is used for quantum, but collapses when transitioning to classical.

Hartman–Grobman theorem:

"In the neighborhood of a hyperbolic fixed point... linearization is effective in predicting qualitative patterns of behavior." – straight from Wikipedia, I didn't change the wording.

Now, notice that if you draw a line from the tip of the lady's nose in the background to the tip of her nose in the 2D picture, and then again to the tip that's in the picture that inside that picture etc. the position of the tip of the nose converges onto a hyperbolic fixed point. This gives us 3 new rhymes.

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Rhyme #4:

Our model: When **zooming in on reality**, materialist physicist **finds a linearization** that is very effective at **helping him make qualitative predictions**.

Actual experience: **when zooming in on reality** materialist physicist **finds a linearization** called Schrodinger's equation that is very effective at **helping him make predictions** about **qualitative** outcomes (yes/no questions-think Wheeler's it from bit description of QM)

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Rhyme #5:

Our model: When zooming out the linearization fails suddenly and all at once. This is because, per HG theorem

(a) the linearization is only used for qualitative predictions, meaning it cannot tell half-truths.

(b) the linearization must tell the truth in the neighborhood of fixed point but need not tell the truth outside this neighborhood.

Actual experience: when zooming out to include interaction with measurement device the wave function satisfying the Schrodinger linearization collapses.

Call this Rhyme #5: Collapse in both HG theorem and QM.

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Rhyme #6:

Our model: If you accept that something like a hyperbolic fixed point is created when physicist zooms in on reality then the neighborhood referenced by HG theorem always follows the physicist's gaze, meaning the physicist can never pin down the boundary between where the linearization that cannot tell a half-truth tells a lie and where it tells a truth.

Actual experience: Copenhagen interpretation of QM famously refuses to say where the boundary is drawn between quantum and classical mechanics.

Call this Rhyme #6: Failure to pin down boundary in both HG and QM.

Last rhyme # 6 itself rhymes with rhyme #2.

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